

Link to this document, version 1: 10.5281/zenodo.8091173

Purpose of this document: describe the fair game

FAIR Game

Learning Objective

- Figure out which drug treats your patient

Game Message

- How FAIR helps federated data analysis

Tutorial

The materials for the game were produced under the EJP RD program for partners, and access may be available upon request:

- Video tutorial: 10.5281/zenodo.8090677
- Presentation tutorial: 10.5281/zenodo.8090587
- Poster: 10.5281/zenodo.8090715
- Workflow: <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/workflows/fair-game-plan>

Reference Implementation

Part 1

- Open Gather.town
 - Gather town game environment - BYOD 2021: <https://app.gather.town/app/MgETX10vjX06OSJd/byod-2021> password:
 - BYOD 2022: <https://app.gather.town/app/1DBK1KU2NqGeFbE6/byod-2022> password: FAIR-BYOD22
 - Fair game working (w/ ontology room): https://app.gather.town/app/hkHRFv0eK8Uckuka/FAIR_Game_working password: FAIR-GAME
- Create your avatar and enter your name
- 'Join the Gathering' with camera and audio
- Follow the quick tutorial to get used to the controls
- Your participant ID is linked to a group, every group is assigned to a registry in a specific country
 - *Show slides with grouping*
- Your participant ID is also linked to a patient
 - *Slides with grouping*
- When you enter Gather.town, find the registry of your country and find the patient chart
 - *Example chart*
- Read the chart and find a treatment for your patient, the treatment is captured in another registry from another country[Text Wrapping Break]

Part 2

- go back to your registry
- go to ontology room
- Repeat the steps of part 1 (try to find the treating drug) but through the ontology room
- find the solution!

Gameplay set up

- Number of participants: 35-40
- 8 groups/registries of 5 patients/participants (NL, IT, FR, ES, SW, CZ, PL, IR)
- Every participant gets a patient assigned
- Every participant is randomly put on the map
- 5 rooms / registries
 - Registries (rooms in Gather.town) are spread across the map, with patients (posters in Gather.town) in them
 - registries / room names are in different languages (e.g. AMC registry, LUMC registry, color, city,)
- participant is a doctor trying to find a cure to one assigned patient
 - group patients or each doctor has its own patient?
- 40 patients, 5 different symptoms, 5 treatment options (one to each symptom)
- randomize items on cards (+ place predicates in different languages)
- Logic: find the correct treatment to each symptom
 - 1st part cards in languages including metadata
 - ontologies explained throughout the course
 - 2nd part cards are in english with ontology codes

Rules

- Do not use external sources

Challenges

- different languages
- ontologised information
 - show its absence in part 1
 - 'work with' in part 2

Solution

- decode the tamil card with the ontology that you learn in the course
- extra poster where you explain label for tamil card

Design

- 5 Avatar next to a bed or poster
- 4 patients are clue to other rooms

- 1 patient is the tamil one (to solve)
- 1 language per room (PT, Tamil, NL, EN,)
- distractions / decoration
- Europe map image as background
- Sign posts in the map as entrance
- “ontology room” decoding bio portal room locked until last day as Switzerland

Editions and Credits

- First edition of the FAIR data Game during the “Rome Summer School, ISS” September 2021, Online
 - During the second training module of the International Summer School on Rare Disease Registries and FAIRification of Data
 - Programme <https://www.ejprarediseases.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Summ-School-RD-Registries-FAIRification-of-Data-Prog-Ed2021.pdf>
 - Conceptualization: Marco Roos, Bruna Vieira, Claudio Carta, César Bernabé, all FAIRification Stewards.
 - Presentation of first edition fair game: Bruna Vieira, César Bernabé, Martijn Kersloot, Rajaram Kaliyaperumal, Claudio Carta, Marco Roos & the EJP RD FAIRification Stewards
 - Design of game environment in Gather town: Bruna dos Santos Vieira, César Bernabé, and Alberto Cámara.
 - Functionality of queries and ontologies: Rajaram
 - Licensing w Gathertown for servers Rome Summer school: Bruna dos Santos Vieira, Martijn Kersloot
 - Video Tutorial: Alberto Cámara
 - Text tutorial: Bruna Vieira, Martijn Kersloot,
 - During game support: all FAIRification stewards
- SWAT4HCLS, February 2022, online:
 - <https://www.swat4ls.org/workshops/leiden2022/scientific-programme2022/>
 - Licensing and Payment of Gathertown license for swat4hcls: Bruna (via Scott Marshal), César and Marco
 - Poster Conceptualization: Claudio Carta
 - Poster Editing and design: Bruna Vieira
 - Design a new environment
 - During game support: all FAIRification stewards
- Second Edition of the FAIR Data Game during the “Rome Summer School, ISS, September 2022
 - During the second training module of the International Summer School on RD registries and FAIRification of data
 - <https://www.ejprarediseases.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Draft-Programme-SumSch-2022-1.pdf>

- Third edition September 2023 - in 3 parts: Accessibility, UnFAIR, FAIR the programme https://www.ejprarediseases.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/23-09-25-Prog-SumSch-RD-Reg-FAIR-Data_2023_Draft_V330.pdf

References

1. Marco Roos et al. (2014), Bring your own data parties and beyond: make your data linkable to speed up rare disease research. RARE DISEASES AND ORPHAN DRUGS An International Journal of Public Health, Volume 1, Number 4, Supplement 4, page 21. Online ISSN 2385-2364. Access URL <https://rarejournal.org/index.php/rarejournal/article/download/69/93>
2. Roos and Lopes, 2017. Linked Registries: Connecting Rare Diseases Patient Registries through a Semantic Web Layer. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/8327980>
3. International Society Studies Vascular Anomalies, ISSVA, 2020, *Vascular Anomaly Registries*, "Video", Youtube, <https://youtu.be/DhwMqM1cM-w>

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